

**A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON THE MANAGEMENT OF
SADHYO VRANA W.S.R. TO TRAUMATIC INJURY**

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ABSTRACT

Sadhyo Vrana, as described in Ayurveda, refers to an acute wound that develops instantly following trauma. It corresponds to modern traumatic injuries caused by mechanical, physical, or accidental factors. An injury is the adverse effect of a physical force upon a person. The force involved in most injuries is mechanical. The incidence of wound trauma is very large globally. The number of patients with wounds presenting to the emergency department and to the general practitioners is more as compared to any other health problem. Occasionally, patients with minor and superficial injuries turn into major complications. Complicated wounds are the major cause of absentees at the working place and hospitalizations. Proper management of Sadhyo Vrana is essential to prevent complications like infection, delayed healing, chronic ulceration, and scarring. This review aims to analyze classical Ayurvedic concepts alongside contemporary surgical and wound management principles to establish an integrative approach for better outcomes in the management of

traumatic injuries.

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